

2024 TRAINING REPORT

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The Netherlands eScience Center has been systematically collecting data on our organised workshops since 2020. The aim is to document the development of the workshops and gather feedback from participants through pre- and post-workshop surveys. This feedback is analysed to gain insights into participant perceptions and experiences.

This report provides insights on workshops organised by the Netherlands eScience Center in 2024.

In 2024, ticket pricing was introduced with the goal to reduce no-shows and offset lunch and organisational costs. Registration numbers initially declined but from Q3 onwards recovered again. The year's average attendance rate went up to 91% - an 18% increase since 2023.

NUMBER OF WORKSHOPS

The eScience Center has taught a total of 30 workshops in 2024.

TOTAL OF

30 Workshops

197 Attendees in internally organised workshops

77% In-person workshops

13 Externally funded workshops

13 Average attendees per workshop

91% Attendance per workshop

Number of attendees increased over the year

ATTENDEES' BACKGROUNDS

The eScience Center organised workshops for participants with various backgrounds.

We clustered our participants into 4 domains according to their background:

- Natural Sciences and Engineering (NES)
- Environmental Sciences and Sustainability (ENV)
- Life Sciences & Health (LSH)
- Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)

DOMAIN OF WORKSHOP ATTENDEES (%)

OCCUPATION OF WORKSHOP ATTENDEES (%)

49 %

PhD Candidates
(compared to
59% in 2023)

18 %

Support staff
(compared to
7% in 2023)

WORKSHOP EVALUATIONS

227 participants evaluated our workshops in the post-workshop survey. The graph below shows the distribution of answers in percentages.

RESPONSES FROM PARTICIPANTS IN A SATISFACTION SURVEY

Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly agree

"The workshop improved my skills on the topic"

"I can immediately apply what I learned in this workshop"

"I would recommend this workshop to others who want to learn about the topic"

SELF-EVALUATION OF COMPETENCE IN PYTHON BEFORE AND AFTER THE WORKSHOP

	Before	After
Novice	24.3%	22.8%
Competent Practitioner	72.3%	74.4%
Expert	3.5%	2.7%

POSITIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE ATTENDEES

WORKSHOP CONTENT

“Snakemake, sphinx, pytest, citing code, reproducibility of code. I did not know about them and I believe that they will make my code much better!”

COLLABORATION

“It was nice to struggle together in the breakout rooms and figure it out. Most of the room sessions had assignments that gave us exactly the right number of conceptual steps to take, so we didn't get stuck for a long time on something.”

HANDS-ON ATTITUDE

“I liked the teamwork because it was hands-on and original. Trying to write code from scratch for the purposes of a new analysis was fun.”

INSTRUCTORS

“I really appreciated the fact that any question was ok to ask. The teachers all worked together in trying to answer our questions as best as possible. It also helped that the lecturers had different areas of expertise.”

ATMOSPHERE

“Well organised to keep everyone engaged, and promote critical thinking.”
“Icebreakers at the start of the session. Really puts a smile on everyone's face! Thanks :)”

TRAINING MATERIALS OVERVIEW

The eScience Center actively maintains and develops training materials in the areas of our expertise together with a global community of lesson developers.

13

Number of lessons that we currently maintain

Our training materials

- Parallel programming with Python
- Introduction to Deep Learning
- GPU programming
- Introduction to geospatial raster and vector data with Python
- Good practices in research software development
- Collaborative version control with Git and GitHub
- AI-assisted coding with Codium
- Intermediate research software development with Python
- Machine learning in Python with sikit-learn
- Medical image processing
- Fundamentals of natural language processing
- Research software support platform
- Efficient computing with Julia
- Reproducible research with R packages

IMPACT OF TRAINING MATERIALS

All material is open-source and freely available and can be used in anyone's teaching. What is the impact of that?

This year, the 'Introduction to deep learning with Python' lesson was accepted as an official Carpentries Lab lesson. The Carpentries Lab is a place for high-quality, stable, peer-reviewed, open-source lessons, meaning that the lesson gets the recognition it deserves.

POPULARITY OF OUR TRAINING MATERIAL ON GITHUB

	# stars	# forks
Geospatial Python	159	56
Intermediate Python	54	68
Deep learning intro	33	39
GPU programming	25	13
R packaging	5	10
Research software support	3	4
Other	10	5

WORKSHOPS OUTSIDE OF THE ESCIENCE CENTER USING OUR LESSON MATERIAL

Last year, we started requesting users to let us know when other workshops are taught using our materials.

Although this is not a complete picture, it gives an indication of our workshops' broader impact in the scientific community.

2024 SUMMARY

30

Workshops

15

Different
workshop
topics

13

Different
lessons
maintained

“Intro to deep
learning” lesson
accepted in
Carpentries Lab

23

In-person
workshops

7

Online
workshops

13

Externally
funded workshops

197

Total number of
workshop attendees

13

Average attendees
per workshop

Participant feedback

93%

was happy with
the quality of the
workshop

91%

found that the
workshop improved
their skills

92%

would recommend
the workshop to
others

LET'S STAY IN TOUCH

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